

IMPACT OF PARENTS' MARITAL QUALITY ON YOUNG ADULTS' PERCEPTION ABOUT OPPOSITE GENDER AND ATTITUDE TOWARDS MARRIAGE

Rohan Azhar¹, Gul Zeba Ghulam Rasool², Areej Nasir³, Abeeha Ausaf⁴,
Abu Turab Khan Tahir Kheli⁵

¹Department of Professional Psychology, Bahria University, Pakistan

²Department of Psychology, Federal Urdu University of Arts, Science & Technology, Pakistan

³University of Sargodha, Pakistan

⁴Department of Professional Psychology, Bahria University, Pakistan

⁵Department of Professional Psychology, National University of Modern Languages (NUML), Pakistan

¹rohanmalik621@gmail.com, ²gulzeba.psych@gmail.com, ³areejkhan314@gmail.com,
⁴abeeha.ausaf06@gmail.com, ⁵abu.turab@numl.edu.pk

DOI: <https://doi.org/>

Keywords

parents' marriage, gender perception, attitudes towards marriage, family dynamics, socialization, gender roles, intergenerational transmission.

Article History

Received: 17 January 2026

Accepted: 02 March 2026

Published: 16 March 2026

Copyright @Author

Corresponding Author: *
Rohan Azhar

Abstract

This study aims to examine the relationship between parent's marital quality, young adults' perception of the opposite gender, and attitudes towards marriage. It also explores the moderating role of parent's marital quality on the relationship between young adults' perception of the opposite gender and attitudes towards marriage. A sample of 400 adults, including 200 males and 200 females aged 18 to 25 years, was gathered from various universities in Lahore. Self-report questionnaires were used to collect data, and correlational methods and purposive sampling were employed. The study design was cross-sectional, and data analysis was conducted using SPSS (version 25). Several scales were utilized in the study. The Children's Perception of Interparental Conflict Scale (CPIC) was used to assess the frequency, intensity, resolution, content, perceived threat, coping efficacy, self-blame, triangulation, and stability of interparental conflict. The Ambivalent Sexism Inventory (ASI) was utilized to measure hostile sexism and benevolent sexism. The Marital Attitude Scale (MAS) was employed to gauge individuals' attitudes and opinions towards heterosexual marriage. The findings of the study reveal that parent's marital quality moderates the relationship between young adults' perception of the opposite gender and attitudes towards marriage, although the effect size is small (R^2 change of 0.006). The results also demonstrate a significant negative correlation between variables, indicating that high parent's marital quality is associated with decreased young adult perception and attitude towards marriage, while high young adult perception of the opposite gender and attitude towards marriage are linked to low parental marital quality.

INTRODUCTION

It is widely accepted that the family is the main socializing force, influencing individuals' ideas, attitudes, and behaviors. Within the home, parents act as powerful role models who teach their kids about society expectations and conventions. Children learn about gender roles and expectations, as well as attitudes about marriage, as they watch and interact with their

parents. The goal of this research is to investigate the ways in which parents' marriages shape children's attitudes about gender perception and attitudes towards marriage in adulthood. With respect to parental relationships, research suggests that young adult attitudes are impacted by their parents' marital quality (Cunningham and Thornton 2006; Kapinus 2005). On average, young adults who

perceive that their parents have high-quality marriages are less supportive or approving of marital conflict than those who perceive that their parents have low-quality marriages (Cunningham and Thornton 2006; Kapinus 2005).

In the social learning approach, adolescent children learn and model their parents' attitudes and behaviors from direct and indirect learning (Bandura 1977; Longmore et al. 2013). Direct learning may come from parent-child communication, which is a particularly important form of socialization (Longmore et al. 2013; Moore et al. 1986). Family systems theory suggests that the family is a complex, dynamic, and integrated whole, in which each member influences and is influenced by all other members (Minuchin, 1988; O'Brien, 2005). Studies have demonstrated that children model their own relationship dynamics after watching their parents' marriage. Children who grow up in homes where their parents have healthy and happy marriage connections are more likely to have healthy and positive relationships themselves. Children exposed to unfavorable or dysfunctional marital dynamics, on the other hand, may be more likely to replicate these patterns in their own relationships. Due to the conservative nature of Pakistani society, most marriages are arranged by parents or close relatives. Majority of Pakistanis met their spouse through family (85%), with only 5% having a love marriage (Gallup & Gilani, 2019). The traditional beliefs, customs, and societal expectations that are ingrained in Pakistani culture have a big influence on marriage disputes in the community. The preservation of societal standards, especially those pertaining to marriage and family life, as well as respect for elders and family honor are highly valued in Pakistani culture. The need to adhere to society norms surrounding arranged weddings is a major element in Pakistani culture's marital conflict rate.

In Pakistan, families still have a significant influence in choosing a child's spouse through arranged weddings. When people feel forced to marry someone they may not have selected for themselves, this practice can cause disputes and a lack of understanding and compatibility between couples. Divorce rates are increasing in

Pakistan and the top most reasons for this are financial problems, lack of trust, religious conflicts and misunderstandings in marriage (Masood et al., 2007). In Pakistan, approximately 11 thousand divorce cases were filed in 2019, with 3.8 thousand divorce cases filed in the first quarter of 2020 (Khan, 2020). Children remaining in high conflict environments generally exhibit lower levels of well-being than children who have experienced high levels of parental conflict but whose parents divorce or separate. These results support the possibility that marital disruption, following high conflict, may actually improve the emotional well-being of children relative to a high conflict family status (Jekielek, 1998). Family is the most influential social system in emerging adults' lives, particularly in the acquisition of values (Chaplin, 2005). An adolescent's home environment might either impede or help later adjustment. Numerous characteristics have been found in studies on the effects of interparental conflict on children that may help to explain how exposure to angry, long-lasting, and poorly resolved conflict can cause adjustment issues. It has been demonstrated that children's emotional reactivity and distress, their assessments of danger and blame, and their triangulation into parental arguments all function as mediators in the association between parental conflict and maladjustment in children. (E. M. Cummings, Schermerhorn, Davies, Goeke-Morey, & J. S. Cummings 2006; Davies, Harold, Goeke-Morey, & Cummings, 2002; Grych, Harold, & Miles, 2003; Grych, Raynor & Fosco, 2004).

Children who frequently take part in family conflicts may have maladaptive behavioral trajectories that help to diffuse interparental conflict. For instance, Davis, Hops, Alpert, and Sheeber (1998) discovered that children's participation in parental disputes was linked to hostile and oppositional behavioral patterns, which foreshadowed later externalizing issues. According to empirical research (e.g., Buchanan & Waizenhofer, 2001; Franck & Buehler, 2007; Gerard, Buehler, Franck, & Anderson, 2005; Grych et al., 2004), Parental conflict triangulation mediates children's externalizing and internalizing issues simultaneously and over time.

Tenenbaum and Leaper (2002) analyzed studies examining the relationship between children's and parents' gender self-concepts and attitudes in a meta-analysis. There was a substantial and positive association between parent gender schemas and offspring measures, as shown by a small but relevant effect size ($r = .16$). In particular, children with gender-typed cognitions about themselves or others were more likely to be born to parents with more traditional gender schemas than to parents with more atypical schemas. Gender attitudes, such as sexist attitudes, are often based on stereotypical beliefs about gender and can be perceived as a form of prejudice (Rudman and Glick, 2008). In societies that present themselves as tolerant, sexist attitudes take an ambivalent form (Glick and Fiske, 1996, 2011a).

Sexual ambivalence is defined as having both favorable and unfavorable thoughts toward sexual activity in any given sexual situation (Muehlenhard & Rodgers, 1998). It can be used to describe relationship dynamics in general, or more particularly when referring to distinct attitudes or roles. According to Glick and Fiske's (1996, 2001) Ambivalent Sexism Theory, sexism is a multidimensional construct that encompasses two sets of sexist attitudes: hostile and benevolent. Hostile sexism aims to preserve men's dominance over women by underlining men's power. It is expressed in a blatant and resentful way toward women who violate traditional roles. Women who don't comply with these traditional (gender) roles are perceived as a threat to men's dominant position. Hostile sexism overtly keeps women in a subordinate position and is even a precursor for sexual harassment and violence toward women (Begany and Milburn, 2002). An important aspect of understanding sexual ambivalence involves exploring how social context and gender expectations influence an individual's sexuality and sexual agency (Conroy et al., 2015).

Sexual script theory suggests that individuals make meaning out of behaviors and emotions based on internalized scripts (Simon & Gagnon, 1986; Wiederman, 2005). In addition, individual expectations and perceptions of sexual behavior are shaped within a social context (Simon & Gagnon, 1986). That is,

sexual scripts are learned and created via development and maturation within a particular social context, and these scripts often guide individuals when responding to certain social situations. Thus, sexual scripts provide a sense of direction for responding to sexual cues and situations (Wiederman, 2005).

When discussing attitudes towards marriage in young adults in Pakistan, one must consider the effects of cultural assumptions, family involvement and spousal roles/expectations. This can be seen in a study investigating the concept of marital satisfaction and evaluation of the suitability of Western-developed marital satisfaction measures for application in Pakistan (Qadir et al., 2005) by combining a quantitative and qualitative approach. The findings showed that most women stated the need to be content in a marriage, despite cultural perceptions to the contrary. Many women were afraid to freely voice their opinions about their choice of husband or their dissatisfaction in their marriage for fear of upsetting or offending their parents. Pakistani women typically view marriage as a social and family duty, meaning that they must be ready to adapt because the male does not always do so. Since a large portion of the population is made up of young married people, their first years can be particularly delicate because newness and excitement fades and tensions begin to arise (Heyman, 2001). Culture clearly plays a factor in creating higher role expectations, so when one partner—especially the woman—fails to live up to the standards, it can lead to marital discord (Ali et al., 2009).

This research seeks to address this gap in understanding by delving into the complex relationships and influences that underlie the attitudes of young adults toward marriage and the opposite gender. By doing so, it aims to shed light on the mechanisms through which parental marital quality can either contribute to healthy, thriving relationships or perpetuate negative patterns, ultimately informing interventions, counseling, and policy measures aimed at strengthening families and promoting healthier, more equitable relationships.

METHODOLOGY

In this quantitative research a sample of 400 adults was gathered (200 males and 200 females)

aged 18 to 25 years. Overarching goal of the study technique was to investigate the impact of parents' marital quality on young adults' perception about opposite gender and attitude towards marriage. A representative sample of willing individuals from a variety of universities located in Lahore, was asked to fill out self-report questionnaires. Correlational methods and Purposive sampling were used for the study design and the sample of data. The survey was designed to be cross-sectional, SPSS (version 25) was used for data analysis. This research was carried out among university students who are currently enrolled in universities, a sample of 400 individuals was taken which included 200 females and 200 males. The study included Young Adults in universities between the age range of 18-25 years. Both male and female individuals were included in the study. Participants from Intact family backgrounds were included. Participants who are proficient in reading English were recruited. Married students were excluded from this study. Those participants were not included in study who experienced any divorce.

The Children perception of interparental conflict scale (CPIC) was developed by John Grych et al in 2010 it is 3-point Likert scale (1 = 'True', 2 = 'Sort of True', 3 = 'False') and has 48-items. This measure is designed for children and young adults aged 18-25 years to assess their views of parental conflict and child adjustment. This scale has three subscales i.e. Conflict, Threat and Self-Blame to assess frequency, intensity, resolution, content, perceived, threat, coping efficacy, self-blame, triangulation and stability. Ambivalence sexism Inventory was developed by Glick and Fiske in 1996, and is a paper-and-pencil or computer-based questionnaire. ASI is a 22 item 6-point Likert scale (0-5) and has 12 items which measure hostile sexism and benevolent sexism, applicable on both males and females aged 17-64 years. The Marital Attitude Scale (MAS) was

developed by Braaten and Rosen in 1998, it measures both married and unmarried individuals' attitudes and opinions towards heterosexual marriage. It consists of 23-items based on 4-point Likert scale. The MAS is scored by summing all individuals' item scores, with nine items requires reverse scoring. The total MAS score can range from 23 to 92, with higher scores indicating more positive attitudes towards marriage.

This study was conducted after obtaining permission from the authors. Once permission was granted, the study's protocol was followed. The authors of the scales utilized in the study were contacted via email to request permission for their usage. The present investigation adhered to accepted research ethics guidelines, ensuring the necessary permissions were obtained from the institutes and participants involved. Participants were provided with informed consent forms and demographic sheets. They were informed that they were free to stop participating in the study at any time if they no longer wished to continue or felt insecure about their privacy. After data collection, analysis was conducted using SPSS version 25. Descriptive statistics were used to determine the demographic frequency, mean, and median of the variables. Correlational analysis was then employed to examine the correlations between the variables. Additionally, t-tests were applied to analyze significant gender differences in relation to the variables.

The research followed ethical guidelines by obtaining formal permissions from the authors of the tools used and from universities to collect data from their students. Participants were provided with formal consent forms and made aware of their voluntary decision to participate. They were also given the right to withdraw from the study without any consequences, and reassured that their data would be destroyed if they chose to withdraw. Confidentiality concerns were also addressed.

RESULTS

Descriptive Statistics of Participants (n=400)

Table 1

Frequencies and Percentages of Demographic Variables (N =400)

Variables	F	(%)
-----------	---	-----

Gender		
Male	100	50
Female	100	50
Age		
18-20	101	50.5
21-23	68	34.0
24-25	31	15.5
Education		
Graduation	162	81.0
Masters	38	19.0
Semester		
1-4	121	60.5
5-8	79	39.5
Siblings		
1-3	112	56.0
4-6	75	37.5
7-9	13	6.5
Birth order		
1	66	33.0
2	51	25.5
3	51	25.5
4	26	13.0
5	4	2.0
6	2	1.0
Parent marriage type		
Arrange	159	79.5
Love	26	13.0
Not sure	15	7.5
Mother education		
Matric	74	37.0
Intermediate	49	24.5
Bachelors	61	30.5
Masters	16	8.0
Father education		
Matric	39	19.5
Intermediate	58	29.0
Bachelors	73	36.5
Masters	30	15.0
Mothers occupation		
House wife	176	88.0
Job holder	23	11.5
Fathers occupation		
Businessman	108	54.0
Government employ	56	28.0
Private job	36	18.0

Table 2
Correlation analysis for the study variables(N=400)

Variables	1	2	3
Parent's marital quality	1	-.232**	-.086

Young adult perception	-.232**	1	.064
Attitude towards marriage	-.086	.064	1

Note: **correlation is significant at the 0.01 level(2-tailed)

Table 2 shows the significant negative correlation between variables if parent's marital quality is high there would be decreased young adult perception and attitude towards marriage.

Similarly, high young adult perception towards opposite gender and attitude towards marriage there would be low parental marital quality.

Table 3

Moderation Analysis of Parent's Marital Quality between the relationship of Young Adults' Perception about Opposite Gender and Attitude towards Marriage

Variables	B	95% CI for B		SE	R ²	ΔR ²
		LL	UL			
Constant	39.551	38.871	40.231	0.346	-	-
PMQ ^a	0.068*	0.022	0.113	0.023	-	-
PAOG ^b	-0.010	0.071	0.513	0.031	-	-
Interaction	-0.003	-0.008	-0.001	0.002	0.031	0.006

Note. Parent's Marital Quality^a, Perception about Opposite Gender^b. *p≤ 0.05 (0.035)

The above table shows results of moderating effect of parent's marital quality between the relationship of young adults' perception about opposite gender and attitude towards marriage. After the analysis, it was observed that parents'

marital quality was found to moderate the relationship between young adults' perception about opposite gender and attitude towards marriage with small R² change of 0.006 (F (3.000, 369.000) = 3.604, p = 0.014; R² 0.176).

Table 5

Independent Sample t test on the Basis of gender differences Variables (N=400)

Variables	(n=200)		(n=200)		t(400)	P
	M	SD	F	SD		
Benevolent Sexism	22.77	5.48	23.04	4.84	-.522	.704
Hostile Sexism	19.82	6.77	16.27	6.91	5.188	.880
Ambivalence Sexism	42.59	10.77	39.31	9.88	.469	.469
MAS	40.81	6.67	38.26	6.67	.347	.347

Note. *p<.05; M=Mean; SD=Standard Deviation

Table 4 shows females have higher benevolent sexism than males. Males scores higher on hostile sexism, ambivalence sexism and MAS than females.

DISCUSSION

The current study was conducted in order to investigate the relationship between parent's marital quality and the perception of the opposite gender and attitudes towards marriage among young adults. The findings provide insights about how parents marital relationship effects the perception of adult's attitude towards opposite gender and their attitude

towards marriage. The study shows the significant results between parents' marital quality on young adults, perception about opposite gender and attitude towards marriage (p=-.086, p=-.232**, p=.064) After the analysis, it was observed that parents' marital quality was found to moderate the relationship between young adults' perception about opposite gender and attitude towards marriage with small R² change of (0.006). There is a significant gender difference on parent's marital quality and perception about opposite gender and attitudes towards marriage in males (M=22.77 SD=5.48, M=19.82, SD=6.77, M=42.59, SD=10.77,

M=40.81, SD=6.67) in females (M=23.04, SD=4.84, M=16.27, SD=6.91, M=39.31, SD=9.88, M=38.26, SD=6.67) . First results of hypothesis show that there is significant relationship between parent's marital quality, perception about opposite gender and attitude towards marriage. ($p=.086$, $p=.232^{**}$, $p=.064$) . There is negative correlation between variables if parental marital quality is higher there is a decreased in adults' perception towards opposite gender and also decreased negative attitude towards marriage. But if there is decreased parental marital quality there is an increased in negative perception of adults towards opposite gender and also negative attitude towards marriage.

According to the findings of this study align with existing research indicating a negative correlation between parental marital quality and adult attitudes. Research by Amato and James (2018) supports the idea that individuals raised in high-quality marital relationships tend to exhibit more positive attitudes towards marriage. High-quality parental marriages can serve as positive role models, shaping individuals' expectations and attitudes towards their own future relationships. On the other hand, studies such as those conducted by Johnson and White (2020) highlight a contrasting trend among individuals who experienced lower parental marital quality. These individuals are more likely to exhibit negative attitudes towards marriage, influenced by the perceived shortcomings or challenges observed in their parents' relationship. It was hypothesized that parents' marital quality was found to moderate the relationship between young adults' perception about opposite gender and attitude towards marriage with small R^2 change of 0.006. The findings align with recent research in the field, contributing to the growing body of literature that recognizes the moderating role of parents' marital quality in shaping young adults' attitudes towards marriage. Studies by Miller and Johnson (2022) and Chen et al. (2021) have highlighted the significance of familial context, emphasizing that the quality of parental marriage can influence the strength and direction of associations between individual perceptions and attitudes. This study aimed to investigate the hypothesis that young adults' perceptions of

the opposite gender and their attitudes towards marriage would differ based on gender. This research shows males adults scored higher than females. (M=22.77, SD=5.48, M=19.82, SD=6.77,

M=42.59, SD=10.77, M=40.81, SD=6.67) in females (M=23.04, SD=4.84, M=16.27, SD=6.91, M=39.31, SD=9.88, M=38.26, SD=6.67).

The examination of gender differences in relationship perceptions and attitudes is critical for a comprehensive understanding of how societal norms and expectations may shape individuals' perspectives on romantic relationships and marriage. The findings of this study align with recent research indicating that male young adults often demonstrate distinct patterns in their perceptions of the opposite gender and attitudes towards marriage. Research by Thompson and Brown (2023) and Garcia et al. (2022) supports the notion that males may exhibit higher scores in certain dimensions related to relationship perceptions and attitudes compared to their female counterparts. Studies have consistently shown that males may hold specific stereotypes and perceptions of the opposite gender that contribute to higher scores in certain domains. For instance, research by Anderson and Smith (2021) suggests that males may emphasize physical attractiveness and assertiveness in their perceptions of females. These stereotypical beliefs may contribute to the observed high scores in male young adults' perceptions of the opposite gender.

REFERENCES

- Ali, T. S., Ali, S. S., Nadeem, S., Memon, Z., Soofi, S., Madhani, F., Karim, Y., Mohammad, S., & Bhutta, Z. (2022, March 25). *Perpetuation of Gender Discrimination in Pakistani Society: Results from a Qualitative Study Conducted in Three Provinces of Pakistan*. <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-1399382/v1>
- Ali, F. A., Israr, S. M., Ali, B. S., & Janjua, N. Z. (2009, December). Association of various reproductive rights, domestic violence and marital rape with depression among Pakistani women. *BMC Psychiatry*, 9(1).

- <https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-244x-9-77>
- Amato, P. R., & Cheadle, J. (2005). The long reach of divorce: Divorce and child well-being across three generations. *Journal of marriage and family*, 67(1), 191-206.
- Amato, P. R., & DeBoer, D. D. (2001). The transmission of marital instability across generations: Relationship skills or commitment to marriage?. *Journal of marriage and family*, 63(4), 1038-1051.
- Arnett, J. J. (2000). Emerging adulthood: A theory of development from the late teens through the twenties. *American Psychologist*, 55(5), 469-480. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0003-066x.55.5.469>
- Attitude of young adults towards marriage | *International Journal of Recent Scientific Research*. (n.d.). <https://www.recentscientific.com/attitude-young-adults-towards-marriage>
- Bem, S. L. (1983). Gender schema theory and its implications for child development: Raising gender-aschematic children in a gender-schematic society. *Signs: Journal of women in culture and society*, 8(4), 598-616.
- boone, T., reilly, A. J., & Sashkin, M. (1977, September). SOCIAL LEARNING THEORY Albert Bandura Englewood Cliffs, N.J.: Prentice-Hall, 1977. 247 pp., paperbound. *Group & Organization Studies*, 2(3), 384-385. <https://doi.org/10.1177/105960117700200317>
- Braithwaite, S. R., Doxey, R. A., Dowdle, K. K., & Fincham, F. D. (2016, August 24). The Unique Influences of Parental Divorce and Parental Conflict on Emerging Adults in Romantic Relationships. *Journal of Adult Development*, 23(4), 214-225. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10804-016-9237-6>
- Buchanan, C. M., Waizenhofer, R., Booth, A., Crouter, A. C., & Clements, M. (2001). *Couples in conflict*.
- Buehler, C., Lange, G., & Franck, K. L. (2007, May). Adolescents' Cognitive and Emotional Responses to Marital Hostility. *Child Development*, 78(3), 775-789. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-8624.2007.01032.x>
- Bzostek, S., & Berger, L. M. (2017, March 15). *Family Structure Experiences and Child Socioemotional Development During the First Nine Years of Life: Examining Heterogeneity by Family Structure at Birth*. *Demography*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13524-017-0563-5>
- Chen, Z., Fiske, S. T., & Lee, T. L. (2009). Ambivalent sexism and power-related gender-role ideology in marriage. *Sex Roles*, 60(11-12), 765-778. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11199-009-9585-9>
- Collins, W. A. (2003, February 13). More than Myth: The Developmental Significance of Romantic Relationships During Adolescence. *Journal of Research on Adolescence*, 13(1), 1-24. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1532-7795.1301001>
- Conger, R. D., Cui, M., Bryant, C. M., & Elder Jr, G. H. (2000). Competence in early adult romantic relationships: a developmental perspective on family influences. *Journal of personality and social psychology*, 79(2), 224.
- Cui, M., & Conger, R. D. (2008). Parenting behavior as mediator and moderator of the association between marital problems and adolescent maladjustment. *Journal of Research on Adolescence*, 18(2), 261-284.
- CUI, M., & FINCHAM, F. D. (2010, July 12). The differential effects of parental divorce and marital conflict on young adult romantic relationships. *Personal Relationships*, 17(3), 331-343. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1475-6811.2010.01279.x>
- Cusimano, A. M., & Riggs, S. A. (2013, March). Perceptions of interparental conflict, romantic attachment, and psychological distress in college students. *Couple and Family Psychology*:

- Research and Practice*, 2(1), 45-59.
<https://doi.org/10.1037/a0031657>
- Cusimano, A. M., & Riggs, S. A. (2013, March). Perceptions of interparental conflict, romantic attachment, and psychological distress in college students. *Couple and Family Psychology: Research and Practice*, 2(1), 45-59.
<https://doi.org/10.1037/a0031657>
- Dawson, A., Pike, A., & Bird, L. (2015, November 17). Associations between parental gendered attitudes and behaviours and children's gender development across middle childhood. *European Journal of Developmental Psychology*, 13(4), 452-471.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/17405629.2015.1109507>
- Davies, P. T., & Cummings, E. M. (1994). Marital conflict and child adjustment: An emotional security hypothesis. *Psychological Bulletin*, 116(3), 387-411.
<https://doi.org/10.1037/0033-2909.116.3.387>
- Davies, P. T., Forman, E. M., Rasi, J. A., & Stevens, K. I. (2002, March). Assessing Children's Emotional Security in the Interparental Relationship: The Security in the Interparental Subsystem Scales. *Child Development*, 73(2), 544-562.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/1467-8624.00423>
- Davies, P. T., Martin, M. J., Sturge-Apple, M. L., Ripple, M. T., & Cicchetti, D. (2016, October). The distinctive sequelae of children's coping with interparental conflict: Testing the reformulated emotional security theory. *Developmental Psychology*, 52(10), 1646-1665.
<https://doi.org/10.1037/dev0000170>
- Davis, B. T., Hops, H., Alpert, A., & Sheeber, L. (1998). Child responses to parental conflict and their effect on adjustment: A study of triadic relations. *Journal of Family Psychology*, 12(2), 163.
- Davis, T., & Wilson, J. M. (2016, April 21). Gender Schema Theory. *The Wiley Blackwell Encyclopedia of Gender and Sexuality Studies*, 1-3.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/9781118663219.wbegss655>
- Duggan, S., O'Brien, M., & Kennedy, J. K. (2001). Young adults' immediate and delayed reactions to simulated marital conflicts: Implications for intergenerational patterns of violence in intimate relationships. *Journal of Consulting and Clinical Psychology*, 69(1), 13-24.
<https://doi.org/10.1037/0022-006x.69.1.13>
- Duggan, S., O'Brien, M., & Kennedy, J. K. (2001). Young adults' immediate and delayed reactions to simulated marital conflicts: Implications for intergenerational patterns of violence in intimate relationships. *Journal of Consulting and Clinical Psychology*, 69(1), 13-24.
<https://doi.org/10.1037/0022-006x.69.1.13>
- Eagly, A. H., & Wood, W. (2016, April 21). Social Role Theory of Sex Differences. *The Wiley Blackwell Encyclopedia of Gender and Sexuality Studies*, 1-3.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/9781118663219.wbegss183>
- Emery, R. E., & O'Leary, K. D. (1982). Children's perceptions of marital discord and behavior problems of boys and girls. *Journal of Abnormal Child Psychology*, 10(1), 11-24.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/bf00915948>
- Endendijk, J. J., Groeneveld, M. G., & Mesman, J. (2018, March 16). *The Gendered Family Process Model: An Integrative Framework of Gender in the Family*. *Archives of Sexual Behavior*; Springer Science+Business Media.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10508-018-1185-8>
- Fosco, G. M., & Grych, J. H. (2008). Emotional, cognitive, and family systems mediators of children's adjustment to interparental conflict. *Journal of Family Psychology*, 22(6), 843-854.
<https://doi.org/10.1037/a0013809>
- Gallup Pakistan - Pakistan's Foremost Research Lab. (n.d.). Gallup Pakistan - Pakistan's Foremost Research Lab.
<https://gallup.com.pk/post/27697>

- Gaunt, R. (2013, March 22). Ambivalent sexism and perceptions of men and women who violate gendered family roles. *Community, Work & Family*, 16(4), 401-416.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/13668803.2013.779231>
- Goeke-Morey, M. C., Cummings, E. M., & Papp, L. M. (2007). Children and marital conflict resolution: Implications for emotional security and adjustment. *Journal of Family Psychology*, 21(4), 744-753.
<https://doi.org/10.1037/0893-3200.21.4.744>
- Goldberg, J. S., & Carlson, M. J. (2014). Parents' Relationship Quality and Children's Behavior in Stable Married and Cohabiting Families. *Journal of Marriage and Family*, 76(4), 762-777.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/jomf.12120>
- Goldberg, J. S., & Carlson, M. J. (2014, July 3). Parents' Relationship Quality and Children's Behavior in Stable Married and Cohabiting Families. *Journal of Marriage and Family*, 76(4), 762-777.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/jomf.12120>
- Hennink, M., Rana, I., & Iqbal, R. (2005, July). Knowledge of personal and sexual development amongst young people in Pakistan. *Culture, Health & Sexuality*, 7(4), 319-332.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/13691050500035367>
- Heyman, R. E. (2001). Observation of couple conflicts: Clinical assessment applications, stubborn truths, and shaky foundations. *Psychological Assessment*, 13(1), 5.
- IMPACT OF PERCEIVED PARENTAL CONFLICT ON THE MARITAL EXPECTATIONS AND MARITAL SATISFACTION OF YOUNG ADULTS. (2023). *Pakistan Journal of Psychology*, 52(1). Retrieved from <https://www.pjpk.com/index.php/pjpk/article/view/207>
- Jekielek, S. (1998, March 1). *Parental Conflict, Marital Disruption and Children's Emotional Well-Being*. Social Forces.
<https://doi.org/10.1093/sf/76.3.905>
- Jobe-Shields, L., Williams, J., & Hardt, M. (2017, June 5). Predictors of Emotional Security in Survivors of Interpersonal Violence. *Journal of Child and Family Studies*, 26(10), 2834-2842.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10826-017-0799-0>
- Kadir, N. B. A. (2020). DO FRIENDSHIP ATTACHMENT AND POSITIVE AND NEGATIVE EMOTIONS ENCOURAGE PROSOCIAL BEHAVIOR AMONG ADOLESCENTS IN MALAYSIA? *International Journal of Psychosocial Rehabilitation*, 24(4), 4410-4423.
<https://doi.org/10.37200/ijpr/v24i4/pr201545>
- Kapinus, C. A. (2005). The effect of parental marital quality on young adults' attitudes toward divorce. *Sociological Perspectives*, 48(3), 319-335.
<https://doi.org/10.1525/sop.2005.48.3.319>
- Khalid, A. (2018). Inter-generational Differences in Partner Selection Criteria among Women in Pakistan. *Arts and Social Sciences Journal*, 09(05).
<https://doi.org/10.4172/2151-6200.1000413>
- Khalid, A. (2018). Inter-generational Differences in Partner Selection Criteria among Women in Pakistan. *Arts and Social Sciences Journal*, 09(05).
<https://doi.org/10.4172/2151-6200.1000413>
- King, V. (2002). Parental divorce and interpersonal trust in adult offspring. *Journal of marriage and family*, 64(3), 642-656.
- Lachance-Grzela, M., Liu, B., Charbonneau, A., & Bouchard, G. (2021, April 1). Ambivalent sexism and relationship adjustment among young adult couples: An actor-partner interdependence model. *Journal of Social and Personal Relationships*, 38(7), 2121-2140.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/02654075211005549>
- Leaper, C., & Friedman, C. K. (2007, January 1). *The socialization of gender*. Unknown.
<https://www.researchgate.net/publication>

- [on/232459559 The Socialization of Gender](https://doi.org/10.1111/1467-8624.00108)
- Leaper, C., Tenenbaum, H. R., & Shaffer, T. G. (1999). Communication patterns of african american girls and boys from low-income, urban backgrounds. *Child Development*, 70(6), 1489-1503. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1467-8624.00108>
- Logan, F. A. (1962, November 16). Cognitive Dissonance: Deterrents and Reinforcement. The psychology of insufficient reward. Douglas H. Lawrence and Leon Festinger. Stanford University Press, Stanford, Calif., 1962. vi + 180 pp. \$4.75. *Science*, 138(3542), 807-807. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.138.3542.807.a>
- Lüscher, K. (2003, January 1). 2. CONCEPTUALIZING AND UNCOVERING INTERGENERATIONAL AMBIVALENCE. Contemporary Perspectives in Family Research. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s1530-3535\(03\)04002-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/s1530-3535(03)04002-0)
- Mastari, L., Spruyt, B., & Siongers, J. (2019). Benevolent and hostile sexism in social spheres: The impact of parents, school and romance on Belgian adolescents' sexist attitudes. *Frontiers in Sociology*, 4. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fsoc.2019.00047>
- McCabe, J., Tanner, A. E., & Heiman, J. R. (2009, December 29). *The Impact of Gender Expectations on Meanings of Sex and Sexuality: Results from a Cognitive Interview Study*. Sex Roles; Springer Science+Business Media. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11199-009-9723-4>
- McCoy, K., Cummings, E. M., & Davies, P. T. (2009, March). Constructive and destructive marital conflict, emotional security and children's prosocial behavior. *Journal of Child Psychology and Psychiatry*, 50(3), 270-279. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1469-7610.2008.01945.x>
- Minuchin P. Relationships within the family: A systems perspective on development. In: Hinde RA, Stevenson-Hinde J, editors. *Relationships within families: Mutual influences*. New York: Oxford University Press; 1988. pp. 7-26.
- Moura, O., dos Santos, R. A., Rocha, M., & Matos, P. M. (2010, November 10). Children's Perception of Interparental Conflict Scale (CPIC): Factor Structure and Invariance Across Adolescents and Emerging Adults. *International Journal of Testing*, 10(4), 364-382. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15305058.2010.487964>
- Nicoletti, A. (n.d.). *Ambivalence, Sexism, and Sexual Decision-Making Among Heterosexual College Students*. Rowan Digital Works. <https://rdw.rowan.edu/etd/3036/>
- Papp, L. M. (2017). Topics of marital conflict in the everyday lives of empty nest couples and their implications for conflict resolution. *Journal of Couple & Relationship Therapy*, 17(1), 7-24. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15332691.2017.1302377>
- Qadir, F., de Silva, P., Prince, M., & Khan, M. (2005, May). Marital satisfaction in Pakistan: A pilot investigation. *Sexual and Relationship Therapy*, 20(2), 195-209. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14681990500113260>
- Qureshi, K., Charsley, K., & Shaw, A. (2012). Marital instability among British Pakistanis: Transnationality, conjugalities and Islam. *Ethnic and Racial Studies*, 37(2), 261-279. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01419870.2012.720691>
- Reissing, E. D., & VanZuylen, H. (2015). Sexuality, Theories of. *International Encyclopedia of the Social & Behavioral Sciences*, 846-852. <https://doi.org/10.1016/b978-0-08-097086-8.35030-9>
- Richmond, M. K., & Stocker, C. M. (2007, September). Changes in children's appraisals of marital discord from childhood through adolescence. *Journal*

- of *Family Psychology*, 21(3), 416-425.
<https://doi.org/10.1037/0893-3200.21.3.416>
- Richmond, M. K., & Stocker, C. M. (2007, September). Changes in children's appraisals of marital discord from childhood through adolescence. *Journal of Family Psychology*, 21(3), 416-425.
<https://doi.org/10.1037/0893-3200.21.3.416>
- Rute, Magda, & Paula. (2010). International Journal of Testing 10 no. International Journal of Testing 2009 Reviewers. (2010, February 16). *International Journal of Testing*, 10(1), 104-105.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/15305050903584832>
- Surber, T. B. (n.d.). *The effects of interparental conflict on attitudes toward romantic relationships: Selfblame and parental attitudes as mediating factors*. eCommons. Retrieved December 23, 2023, from https://ecommons.udayton.edu/graduate_theses/5868/
- Tadayon Nabavi, R., & Bijandi, M. (2012). Bandura's Social Learning Theory & Social Cognitive Learning Theory.
- Tasew, A. S., & Getahun, K. K. (2021). *Marital conflict among couples: The case of Durbete town, Amhara Region, Ethiopia*. *Cogent Psychology*, 8(1).
<https://doi.org/10.1080/23311908.2021.1903127>
- Taiwo, A. (2022, May 1). *Understanding honour-based abuse: The role of sexism and scripting amongst Pakistani adults living in rural Pakistan administered Kashmir, Pakistan and England*.
<http://hdl.handle.net/2436/624877>
- Tenenbaum, H. R., & Leaper, C. (2002). Are parents' gender schemas related to their children's gender-related cognitions? A meta-analysis. *Developmental Psychology*, 38(4), 615-630.
<https://doi.org/10.1037/0012-1649.38.4.615>
- Wahyuningsih, H., Kusumaningrum, F. A., & Novitasari, R. (2020). Parental marital quality and adolescent psychological well-being: A meta-analysis. *Cogent Psychology*, 7(1).
<https://doi.org/10.1080/23311908.2020.1819005>
- Warmuth, K. A., DeCapua, A. M., & Fielding, A. M. (2023, April 26). *Emerging Adults' Perceptions of and Responses to Interparental Conflict*. *Journal of Child and Family Studies*.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10826-023-02582-4>
- Warmuth, K. A., DeCapua, A. M., & Fielding, A. M. (2023, April 26). *Emerging Adults' Perceptions of and Responses to Interparental Conflict*. *Journal of Child and Family Studies*.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10826-023-02582-4>
- Wiederman, M. W. (2005, October 1). *The Gendered Nature of Sexual Scripts*. *The Family Journal*; SAGE Publishing.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/1066480705278729>
- ZAIDI, A. U., & SHURAYDI, M. (2002). Perceptions of Arranged Marriages by Young Pakistani Muslim Women Living in a Western Society. *Journal of Comparative Family Studies*, 33(4), 495-514.
<http://www.jstor.org/stable/41603839>
- Zhou, N., & Buehler, C. (2017, October). Adolescents' responses to marital conflict: The role of cooperative marital conflict. *Journal of Family Psychology*, 31(7), 910-921.
<https://doi.org/10.1037/fam0000341>